

Breathe-in, breathe-out: A correlational study on the level of knowledge and attitude of students towards electronic cigarette smoking

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Abstract

Despite the rising trend of e-cigarette use among the youth, there is a scarcity of data on the knowledge and attitudes of e-cigarette users, especially among young adults in the Philippines. This correlation study aims to assess the level of knowledge and attitude towards e-cigarette smoking among college students. Using simple random sampling, 221 respondents were gathered from the private universities in Intramuros, Manila. Their level of knowledge on e-cigarettes is "Advanced" (39.4%) while their attitude towards e-cigarette smoking is "Slightly Negative" (52.9%). As the level of knowledge towards e-cigarette smoking increases, it is more likely that their attitude to be negative or neutral towards e-cigarette smoking. The two variables have significant positive negligible correlation (0.01 level of significance, $r=0.190$) demonstrating that the level of knowledge on electronic cigarettes can be one of the factors that can affect attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking, among other determining factors. From the conclusions, the recommendations are offered such as reinforcement and inclusion of the harmful effects of electronic cigarettes in anti-smoking campaigns and regulations, as well as schools to strengthen programs and intervention measures to educate students with factual health information on e-cigarette smoking.

Keywords: E-cigarettes; public health; college students; health perception; health information.

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Introduction

Electronic cigarettes (e-cigarettes) or Electronic Nicotine Delivery Systems (ENDS), commonly referred to as vapes, are battery-powered smoking devices that convert vape juice which contains nicotine, flavorings, and other chemicals into inhalable aerosol (NIDA, 2020). Electronic cigarettes are advertised as a healthier alternative to traditional cigarettes (Glasser et al., 2017; Münzel et al., 2020). In contrary, electronic cigarettes are also dangerous and can lead to lung injuries such as pneumothorax (Wieckowska et al., 2021; Borchert et al., 2021). Additionally, smoking electronic cigarettes to cease traditional cigarette smoking only led to using both products (Caraballo et al., 2017).

The proposed Senate Bill 2239 in December 2021 also known as the "Vaporized Nicotine and Non-Nicotine Products & Regulation Act," or "Vape Bill," lowers the age of access restriction from 21 years old to 18 years old for vaping products, such as electronic cigarettes. The Department of Health (DOH) said that the approval of the said bill puts the Filipino youth at risk as vapor products are made enticing and easily accessible as well as it makes young adults more susceptible to smoking initiation and nicotine addiction. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and DOH asserts that this Vape Bill is not a health bill and instead promotes the use of electronic cigarettes among the Filipino youth (Cruz, 2023).

In 2021, the Global State of Tobacco Harm Reduction (GSTHR) reported around 82 million electronic cigarette users worldwide, with a 17% increase from the year 2020. Whereas 2.7 million, or around 3% of the world's electronic cigarette users were Filipinos (Ruperez, 2022). Moreover, the rate of smoking nicotine using electronic cigarettes among college-age adults increased from 6.1% in the year 2017 to 22% in the year 2019 (NIDA, 2019). This shows a trend in electronic cigarette smoking among young adults as electronic cigarettes advertisement strategies focus on reaching the young adult age-group (Pokhrel et al., 2015). The rising popularity of smoking is also present among the Filipino youth. The Global Youth Tobacco Survey has shown a 110 percent increase in electronic cigarette use within the span of four years among the Filipino youth, from 11.7% in 2015 to 24.6% in 2019. Despite the rising prevalence of electronic cigarette use, there is a scarcity of data on the knowledge and attitudes of electronic cigarette users, particularly among young adults in the Philippines (Palmer et al., 2021).

The objective of this study aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and Ambisyon Natin 2040 of advocating healthier well-being for the members of society and provide a long and healthy life, most especially for Filipino young adults, by assessing the knowledge and attitudes of college students who are electronic cigarette smokers to formulate recommendations that can address the public health risk of electronic cigarettes.

Moreover, this study focuses on the students or the young adults with the aim to prevent harmful health-related mentality and habits from persisting towards their later years, which could negatively affect their well-being and that of the next generation.

Statement of the Problem

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents based on their:
 - a. Sex assigned at birth
 - b. Age
 - c. Year level
 - d. Use of traditional cigarettes
 - e. Duration as electronic cigarette smoker
 - f. Frequency of consuming electronic cigarettes
 - g. Average amount spent on electronic cigarettes
 - h. Number of household members who consume electronic cigarette
2. What is the level of knowledge of the respondents towards electronic cigarette smoking?
3. What is the assessment of the respondents on their attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking?
4. Is there a significant relationship in the respondents' assessment on the level of knowledge and attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking?

Scope and Delimitations

This study focuses the knowledge and attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking and only covers current electronic cigarette smokers who are enrolled in college programs in private universities within Intramuros, City of Manila namely: Lyceum of the Philippines University-Manila, Mapua University, and Colegio de San Juan de Letrán. This study excludes data from college students who are non-electronic cigarette smokers. The researchers chose this specific demographic to explore as preventing young adults from starting to smoke is crucial for changing the course of the epidemic for the next generation (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2021).

The data will only be gathered in the Intramuros, City of Manila and therefore do not represent a national proportion, limiting the generalizability of the results of this study. Moreover, this study excludes the current health status, health history for the past 6 months of the respondents as well as their possibility of smoking other forms of burned substances such as marijuana and heated tobacco. This study was conducted within the academic year, beginning in August 2022 until May 2023.

Methodology

Research Design

The purpose of this study was to assess the level of knowledge and attitude of college students in Intramuros, Manila towards electronic cigarette smoking. A descriptive research design was used in this study as this research design focuses on studying and describing individuals, events, or conditions as they are in nature (Siedlecki, 2020). The researchers used non-experimental descriptive research design using a correlational approach to conduct the study.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in private universities in the Intramuros district of Manila which includes Colegio de San Juan de Letran, Mapua University, and Lyceum of the Philippines University-Manila. The researchers have frequently observed that many college students in these universities are electronic cigarette smokers. Hence, private universities in Intramuros, Manila were chosen to be the locale of this research. The study was conducted throughout the academic year 2022-2023.

Sampling Design

Probability sampling using a simple random sampling technique was utilized to determine the group of respondents who participated in the survey. The use of probability sampling in this study gave each member of the population a fair chance of being chosen as a participant, allowing equal distribution of the population of each participating university in Intramuros, Manila.

Instrumentation

A researcher-made questionnaire (refereed) from a study by Aghar et al. (2020) entitled "*Knowledge and attitudes towards e-cigarette use in Lebanon and their associated factors*" was utilized as an instrument of this study to gather necessary data from the respondents and was validated by experts. The questionnaire is composed of 49 items wherein the first section of the questionnaire seeks the respondent's demographic profile. The second section of the questionnaire is answerable by true or false to measure the knowledge of the respondents. Lastly, the third section is answerable by yes or no to interpret the assessment of the respondents of their attitude toward electronic cigarette smoking.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers formally communicated to partner with the student councils of each participating university: Mapua University, Colegio de San Juan de Letran, and Lyceum of the Philippines University-Manila. The researchers sent a letter of intent containing the purpose of the study. The researchers handed over the survey instrument to the student council of each university to facilitate randomly distributing the survey questionnaires to the college population of their respective universities. A total of 221 questionnaires were then gathered, tabulated, cleaned, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment

The researchers made use of the following statistical treatment: Frequency distribution, chi-square, and Pearson's R correlation. The data gathered from the questionnaire were tabulated and processed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Table 1. Verbal Interpretation Guide on the Assessment of Attitude of Electronic Cigarette Smokers

Range	Assessment of Attitude
1 – 2	Extremely Positive
3 – 4	Moderately Positive
5 – 7	Slightly Negative
8 – 10	Moderately Negative
11 – 13	Extremely Negative

Table 2. Verbal Interpretation Guide on the Level of Knowledge in Electronic Cigarettes

Range	Level of Knowledge
0 – 2	Beginner
3 – 5	Developing
6 – 8	Approaching Proficiency
9 – 11	Proficient
12 – 15	Advanced

Table 1 shows the verbal interpretation guide on the assessment of attitudes of electronic cigarette smokers whereas Table 2 shows the verbal interpretation guide on the level of knowledge towards electronic cigarettes.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile

The researchers aimed for 200 respondents and obtained a total of 221 qualified responses from college students in private universities within Intramuros, City of Manila who are current electronic cigarette smokers, consisting of 167 (75.6%) male while there are 49 (22.3%) females and 5 (3%) who preferred not to say their sexuality. Electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila mostly belong to 20 years of age (64 or 29%) followed by 45 (20.4%), 44 (19.9%), 27 (12.12%), 24 (10.9%), and 13 (5.9%) belonging to ages 21, 19, 22, 23, and 18, respectively. Most of the respondents are in their first-year academic year level (65 or 29.4%) and have experience with traditional cigarette smoking (159 or 71.9%).

Almost forty-one percent (40.7% or 90 respondents) have been smoking electronic cigarettes for 1-2 years while 63 (28.5%), 58 (26.2%), 10 (4.5%) of the respondents are electronic cigarette smokers for 3-5 years, less than a year, and more than 5 years, respectively. Almost fifty-three percent (52.9 percent or 117) of the respondents reported using electronic cigarettes 20-30 days/month followed by 58 (26.2%) and 46 (20.8%) with 1-10 days/month and 11-19 days/month, respectively. Almost forty percent (39.8% or 88 respondents) reported to spend an average of Php 300-500 on electronic cigarettes followed by 51 (23.1%), 31 (14%), 27 (12.2%), 24 (10.9%), reported to spend Php 500-700, Php 700-1000, less than Php 300, and more than Php 1000, respectively. Most of the respondents (95 or 43%) noted that they have at least 1-2 household members consuming electronic cigarettes.

Level of Knowledge on Electronic Cigarette Smoking

College students who are electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila have an “Advanced” level of knowledge on electronic cigarettes (87 or 39.4% of the respondents). Whereas 74 or 33.5% of the respondents are “Proficient”, 53 or 24% of the respondents are on “Approaching Proficiency.” Only 6 (2.7%) and 1 (.5%) of the respondents are identified as “Developing” and “Beginner,” respectively, with regards to level of knowledge on electronic cigarettes.

Table 3. Respondents’ Knowledge on Electronic Cigarette Smoking based on Individual Items

Statements	Sum	Percentage
1. Electronic cigarettes are associated with bladder cancer.	100	45.25
2. Electronic cigarettes are FDA approved.	48	21.72
3. Some flavors of electronic cigarettes liquid (e-liquid) are more harmful than others.	156	70.59
4. Swallowing the liquid in electronic cigarettes can accidentally cause poisoning that is potentially fatal.	125	56.56
5. Electronic cigarettes are not associated with lung cancer.	152	68.78
6. Electronic cigarettes impair lung and heart functions.	172	77.83
7. Electronic cigarettes do not contribute to secondhand smoking.	126	57.01
8. Electronic cigarettes can influence fetal development.	157	71.04
9. Nicotine is present in most electronic cigarettes.	206	93.21
10. Harmful flavorings and toxins are found in electronic cigarette aerosol.	168	76.02
11. Electronic cigarettes are harmless.	143	64.71
12. Some components of the liquid found in electronic cigarettes can cause harmful lung conditions.	176	79.64
13. Electronic cigarette flavorings are not addictive.	164	74.21
14. Electronic cigarettes are suitable for pregnant women.	193	87.33
15. Electronic cigarettes are suitable for children.	193	87.33

Table 3 illustrates the level of knowledge of respondents based on specific parameters. The table shows that most college student electronic cigarette smokers (206 or 93.2%) answered item number 9 correctly. This corresponds to the respondents being aware that nicotine is present in most electronic cigarettes. Knowledge on nicotine content provides an avenue for students to diminish usage from traditional modality and eventually shifting use and total eradication. A study by Talhout et al. (2016) demonstrates that the amount of nicotine was the third most common reason reported by electronic cigarette users as a motivating factor for electronic cigarette use, or a factor that influences their perceived efficacy of using electronic cigarettes as a cessation tool.

The items number 14 and 15 were answered correctly by 193 or 87.3% of the respondents, demonstrating that the respondents have knowledge that electronic cigarettes are not beneficial or suitable for pregnant women and the pediatric population. This is concretized by Tobore (2019) stating that e-liquids are associated with inflammation and can lead to oxidative stress that causes DNA repair system alteration and can lead to respiratory, psychiatric, metabolic, and neurodegenerative diseases.

While 176 or 76.64% of the respondents demonstrated high proficiency with the fact that some components of the liquid found in electronic cigarettes cause harmful lung conditions and 172 or 77.8% of the respondents have knowledge that electronic cigarettes impair lung and heart functions. Similarly, a study from McLeish et al. (2022) shows that most college-aged electronic cigarette smokers are aware that electronic cigarette smoking can increase the health risk for cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. The components of electronic cigarette and exposures are associated to damage of the lung tissue, resulting to impairment of viral responses and thus pose higher risk of disease among electronic cigarette users as they cannot adequately fight infection (Scott et al., 2018; Higham et al., 2018; Eshragian & Al-Delaimy, 2020).

On the other hand, item number 2 acquired the lowest correct answer wherein 48 or 21.7% of the respondents answered it correctly. Knowledge on this particular parameter is noted by the fact that most of the respondents have lower proficiency on the FDA approval of electronic cigarettes. Contrary to the perception that electronic cigarettes are FDA approved, no electronic cigarette has been approved as a cessation device by Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as more research is needed to understand the potential risks and benefits of electronic cigarettes (U.S. Food & Drug Administration, 2022) and there is still scarcity of scientific evidence substantiating the effectiveness or safety of electronic cigarettes (WHO, 2020). Additionally, 100 or 45.25% of the respondents answered item number 1 correctly. This demonstrates a lower level of knowledge of the respondents on the association of electronic cigarettes with bladder cancer. Herriges et al. (2022) revealed that bladder cancer was more prevalent among those with traditional cigarette and electronic cigarette smoking history, as compared to never smokers and urine from electronic cigarette users contain carcinogens, chemicals known to cause cancer, and these have strong association with bladder cancer (Bjurlin et al., 2021).

In this study, 126 or 57.01% of the respondents correctly answered item number 7 demonstrating that the respondents are less knowledgeable on the contribution of electronic cigarettes to secondhand smoking. A study by Flouris et al. (2013), cited by Shelton et al. (2022) revealed that the levels of cotinine, the predominant metabolite of nicotine and a biomarker, in those exposed to secondhand vapor from electronic cigarettes is similar to those exposed to secondhand tobacco smoke from traditional cigarettes.

Attitude towards Electronic Cigarette Smoking

The study reveals that college students who are electronic cigarette smokers have a "Slightly Negative" attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking (117 or 52.9%). Whereas 58 or 26.2%, 38 or 17.2%, 7 or 3.2%, and 1 or .5% of the respondents have a "Moderately Positive," "Moderately Negative," "Extremely Positive," and "Extremely Negative" attitudes towards electronic cigarette smoking, respectively. This is especially concerning as they continue to use electronic cigarettes despite their somewhat negative attitude toward electronic cigarette smoking. Similarly, A study by Esteban-Ipac and Torres-Ticzon (2022) further demonstrates this occurrence that despite knowing the dangers of electronic cigarettes, smokers have no objection to continuing to use them.

This result can also be associated with strong attitudes and motivation playing an active role in habit formation (Verplanken & Orbell, 2022). Therefore, this neutrality in attitude of the students does not necessarily imply a strong negative perception to be against electronic cigarette smoking.

Table 4. Respondents' Attitude on Electronic Cigarette Smoking based on Individual Items

Statements	Sum	Percentage
1. Should electronic cigarettes be recommended to a nonsmoker?	164	74.21
2. Do you think electronic cigarettes are harmful for health?	178	80.54
3. Should the use of electronic cigarettes be allowed in places that do not allow smoking?	151	68.33
4. Would you consider someone who uses electronic cigarettes a smoker?	167	75.57
5. Do you think the use of electronic cigarettes can lead to dependence?	144	65.16
6. Do you think electronic cigarettes should be regulated like other tobacco products in work and public places?	157	71.04
7. Do you feel more comfortable using or openly talking about smoking electronic cigarettes, compared to regular cigarettes?	26	11.76
8. Do you feel it is more socially acceptable to smoke electronic cigarettes, compared to regular cigarettes?	42	19.00
9. Should electronic cigarettes be used as a replacement for regular cigarettes?	37	16.74
10. Do you think it is acceptable to experiment with electronic cigarettes for pleasure?	78	35.29
11. Do you think using electronic cigarettes would be an effective way to help in smoking cessation?	25	11.31
12. Do you think it is acceptable to use electronic cigarettes as a smoking cessation method?	36	16.29
13. Do you think electronic cigarettes can help people cut down on cigarettes or quit smoking?	32	14.48

Table 4 shows the highest frequency count of specific items under the attitude variable which reflected the respondents' negative attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking. The respondents have a more negative attitude towards the specific item numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6.

Most college students who are electronic cigarette smokers (178 or 80.54%) are assessed to have a negative attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking particularly reflected in their perception of electronic cigarettes as harmful for their health. This can be seen as a public health challenge given that they persistently smoke electronic cigarettes despite being aware of the health risks of electronic cigarette use. Therefore, illustrates that it is less likely that this awareness influences their decision to cease electronic cigarette smoking. Comparably, Esteban-Ipac and Torres-Ticzon (2022) revealed that despite young adults being knowledgeable about the negative consequences of smoking and secondhand smoke, smoking among this population remains prevalent.

The study reveals that 167 (75.57%) of the respondents consider electronic cigarette users as smokers. Likewise, Al-Sawalha (2021) revealed that electronic cigarette users consider electronic cigarette use as smoking as they perceive electronic cigarettes “safer way” to smoke compared to traditional cigarettes. Additionally, 164 or 74.21% of the respondents have negative attitude on recommending electronic cigarettes to a nonsmoker; 157 or 71.04% of the respondents think that electronic cigarettes should be regulated like other tobacco products in public premises; and 151 or 68.33% of the respondents have negative attitude on the use of electronic cigarettes in places that do not allow smoking.

On the other hand, 25 or 11.31% of the respondents do not think that electronic cigarettes would be an effective way to help in smoking cessation. This exhibits that most college-aged electronic cigarette smokers in this study have a positive attitude towards the use of electronic cigarettes to aid in smoking cessation. According to Hajek (2014), the high prevalence of electronic cigarette use may be attributed to the positive attitude towards the use of electronic cigarettes to quit traditional cigarettes given that electronic cigarettes have been promoted as reduced-harm products. However, Kalkhoran and Glantz (2016) revealed that electronic cigarette use makes it more difficult to quit traditional cigarette smoking.

A positive attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking was demonstrated with most of the respondents (74 or 88.2%) agreeing to feel more comfortable using or openly talking about smoking electronic cigarettes than traditional cigarettes. With the prevalence of the perception that smoking electronic cigarettes is more accepted as a “safer” or “better” way to smoke than traditional cigarettes, this possibly influenced the respondents to have a rather positive attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking as they can openly talk about it without being criticized by other people. The results align with the study of Leung et al. (2017) which demonstrated electronic cigarette use susceptibility among those who perceived greater attractiveness and better acceptability of electronic cigarettes than traditional cigarettes. Moreover, better parental and school acceptability of electronic cigarette use than traditional cigarette smoking was associated with electronic cigarette use susceptibility. Correspondingly, Puteh et al. (2018) revealed that social influence and current trends are two of the reasons for electronic cigarette use by dual users.

Correlation Between Level of Knowledge and Attitude towards Electronic Cigarette Smoking

Table 5. Chi-Square Test Result on Level of Knowledge and Attitude towards Electronic Cigarette Smoking

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	28.602*	16	.027
Likelihood Ratio	28.242	16	.030
Linear-by-Linear Association	10.491	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	221		

a. 16 cells (64.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

Using the Chi-square test, a p-value of .030 shows a significant correlation between the level of knowledge and attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking among the college students who are electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila.

This shows that the respondent’s knowledge of electronic cigarettes can be a factor that affects attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking. According to a study conducted by Mayorga et al. (2018) daily electronic cigarette users try to justify their attitude toward electronic cigarettes by ignoring or underestimating the negative effects and health risks of electronic cigarette smoking while focusing on the positive effects and benefits of electronic cigarette smoking. Thus, cognitive dissonance plays a major role in affecting the attitude of the respondents toward electronic cigarette smoking despite being aware of the possible health risk and this phenomenon poses a health concern that needs to be addressed.

Table 6. Pearson Moment Correlation Result

	Variables	Knowledge on E-cigarettes	Attitude towards E-cigarette smoking
Knowledge on E-cigarettes	Pearson correlation	1	.190**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.005
	N	221	221
Attitude towards E-cigarette smoking	Pearson correlation	.190**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	
	N	221	221

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Whereas the use of Pearson moment correlation resulted at 0.01 level of significance with r-value of .190 and interprets that there is a significant positive negligible correlation between the level of knowledge and attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking among the college students who are electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila.

Moreover, this denotes that the level of knowledge on electronic cigarettes of the respondents can be one of the factors that can affect their attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking, among other determining factors. The result of the study shows that the respondents who appeared to have a higher level of knowledge have a slightly negative attitude. Therefore, as the respondents’ level of knowledge towards electronic cigarette smoking increases, it is more likely that their attitude to be negative or neutral towards electronic cigarette smoking.

Wang et al. (2022) affirms that knowledge has positively influenced the attitude of young adults towards the intention to use electronic cigarettes. However, there are still electronic cigarette smokers who are still willing to purchase and use electronic cigarettes, despite their high level of knowledge on electronic cigarettes and its harmful implications. While the assessed attitude of the respondents is associated with their level of knowledge towards electronic cigarettes, this may not be the sole determinant of their attitude towards the use of electronic cigarettes.

Table 7. Correlation between Level of Knowledge on Electronic Cigarette Smoking and Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variable	P-value	Verbal Interpretation
Sex assigned at birth	Level of Knowledge on E-Cigarette	.510	No Significant Correlation
Age		.875	No Significant Correlation
Year level		.038	Significant Correlation
Use of traditional cigarettes		.262	No Significant Correlation
Duration as electronic cigarette smoker		.369	No Significant Correlation
Frequency of consuming electronic cigarettes		.906	No Significant Correlation
Average amount spent on electronic cigarettes		.492	No Significant Correlation
Number of household members who consume electronic cigarette		.980	No Significant Correlation

Table 7 illustrates that there is a significant correlation between the year level of the respondents and their level of knowledge towards electronic cigarette smoking ($p=.038$). The results of the study demonstrate a lower level of knowledge among the respondents who are in their higher academic year levels.

Peers can influence one's knowledge seeking, as the respondents acquire peers throughout their university years with the same interest in electronic cigarette smoking, this can possibly be a factor that influenced the respondents' absorption and seeking of knowledge thus it is inevitable to potentially construct misconceptions throughout their years of stay in university. The sharing of information influences knowledge and decision-making. Laursen and Veenstra (2023) revealed that students have become affected by peer pressure, which starts in school and people are less likely to use certain systems when their peers are opposed to that system (Taylor & Todd, 1995; de Haan (2013). Therefore, in case of agreement among peers about whether a system should be used, this can enhance the use of that system and sharing of knowledge within peers is more likely.

This can also be associated with the lack of effective anti-smoking advocacy, policies, and/or initiatives of the universities and the local government units to educate electronic cigarette smokers on electronic cigarette smoking and smoking cessation within the university and community premises. According to Backhaus et al. (2017), school is an environment that shows significant effects on learners' life choices and electronic cigarette use at schools with a policy were found to be significantly lower compared to schools without policy (Milicic et al., 2018). Furthermore, anti-smoking campaigns resulted in lessening the intention of smokers to engage in smoking and revealed to have long term benefits to students (Chauhan & Sharma, 2017).

Table 8. Correlation between Attitude towards Electronic Cigarette Smoking and Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Variable	P-value	Verbal Interpretation
Sex assigned at birth	Attitude towards Electronic Cigarette Smoking	.031	Significant Correlation
Age		.344	No Significant Correlation
Year level		.056	No Significant Correlation
Use of traditional cigarettes		.366	No Significant Correlation
Duration as electronic cigarette smoker		.940	No Significant Correlation
Frequency of consuming electronic cigarettes		.602	No Significant Correlation
Average amount spent on electronic cigarettes		.180	No Significant Correlation
Number of household members who consume electronic cigarette		.732	No Significant Correlation

Table 8 shows that the respondents' attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking has a significant relationship with their sex ($p=.031$). The results demonstrate that a significant number of respondents from the male group were assessed to have a moderately positive attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking which is higher than from the group of female respondents.

Male college students possibly have a lesser sense of the possible risks caused by electronic cigarettes that leads them into usage and having a more positive attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking. Aligning to this result, Aghar et al. (2020) found that male sex were predictors of a good attitude toward electronic cigarettes. Similarly, a study by Shaikh et al. (2017) cited by Palmes et al. (2021) stated that compared to females, male participants had a more favorable attitude toward electronic cigarette smoking. While the respondents identified as females are more likely to consider information on cigarettes and the like as taboos (Palmes et al., 2021) and this is another possible factor that may influence their rather negative attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking.

Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, among the college students in Intramuros, Manila, males predominantly smoke electronic cigarettes and currently in their first academic year level which commonly reported current or former use of traditional cigarettes and daily use of electronic cigarettes.

A significant relationship was found between the level of knowledge and attitude of college students who are electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila. College students who are electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila have an "Advanced" level of knowledge towards electronic cigarette smoking.

They have high knowledge on the effects of electronic cigarette usage and the presence of nicotine in electronic cigarettes. However, they are less knowledgeable on the association of electronic cigarettes with bladder cancer, FDA approval of electronic cigarettes, the health risk of swallowing e-liquid, and the contribution of electronic cigarettes to secondhand smoking. On that note, it can also be concluded that having proficient knowledge on electronic cigarettes and its negative consequences does not necessarily lead to decision of electronic cigarette smoking cessation.

College students who are electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila have a "Slightly Negative" attitude towards electronic cigarette smoking. The neutrality in attitude of electronic cigarette smokers in the study shows that they do not have strong negative perception to be against electronic cigarette smoking and initiate cease usage.

College students who are electronic cigarette smokers in Intramuros, Manila consider electronic cigarette users as smokers and think that electronic cigarettes should not be recommended to a nonsmoker, should not be used in places that prohibit smoking, and electronic cigarettes should be regulated like other tobacco products in public premises. However, they feel more comfortable using or openly talking about electronic cigarettes compared to traditional cigarettes.

The researchers offer the following recommendations:

1. The Department of Health (DOH) and Commission on Higher Education (CHED) shall amend and tailor anti-smoking policies and awareness intervention measures that target misconceptions about electronic cigarettes' safety and usage for the younger populations. Together with Food and Drug Administration (FDA), Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), and Local Government Units (LGUs) should rightly regulate selling of electronic cigarettes in electronic cigarette selling points to potentially lessen the perception that it is more socially acceptable due to the easy accessibility of college students to electronic cigarettes. Also, enhance intervention to reach and raise awareness among online sellers that sell electronic cigarettes online given that young populations may utilize the means of online modes of purchasing electronic cigarettes.
2. Launch and/or strengthen school programs and intervention measures that includes electronic cigarettes education, cessation promotion, and awareness on the harms of electronic cigarettes to educate students during their university years. Also, include in university curriculum factual information on the harm of electronic cigarette as a way to curb electronic cigarette smoking among college students.
3. Include graphic health warnings on electronic cigarette packaging aligning to the existing Graphic Health Warnings (GHW) Law or R.A. No. 10643 to extend awareness on harmful health risks of electronic cigarettes that are less known by electronic cigarette smokers in this study.

4. No advertisements on widely accessible mediums are recommended to possibly lessen exposure and influences that may possibly lead to curiosity and ultimately imitation of electronic cigarette smoking. School officials, faculty members, and staff - being considered as second parents of students in the university - should also set an example to the students by having an unfavorable impression towards electronic cigarette smoking and avoiding being seen engaging in electronic cigarette smoking to potentially improve the students' perception on social acceptability of electronic cigarettes. Parents are also recommended to oppose electronic cigarette smoking and lessen influences within the household to avoid leading their children into electronic cigarette use.
5. Lastly, for future researchers to further investigate other factors that were not discussed in this study that may have a significant contribution to determining the attitudes of electronic cigarette smokers.

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